

Can Copaxone™ be Viagra™? On branding innovative drugs through design

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Abstract:

In a world of intense competition and continuous innovation companies often make substantial investments in branding their offerings. Yet creating product brands is no small task, especially when the offering has a limited physical manifestation such as in the case of drugs: naturally importance is placed on package insert that documents the drug safety and efficacy much before any attention is given to the design of the package. Our global study looked to understand if and how *can design augment and reinforce branding a product that's known more for its intellectual assets than physical ones*. Possible relationships of attributes that promote desired drug personalities and *color* design choices were examined across eleven jurisdictions making this global inquiry first in its kind in the pharmaceutical industry. Overall, color-attribute associations were found to be consistent within geographies with a limited set of relationships that showed universal properties. Results are reported and implications to product brands are offered.

1. Introduction

Copaxone™ was introduced by Teva in the mid 90s as the most effective agent for treating Multiple Sclerosis in adults. Viagra™ was brought to market by Pfizer in 1998 to treat male erection problems. One tablet is white, the other is blue. Both drugs are efficacious, leading brands in their field. Both drugs target a global audience in multiple geographic and cultural contexts. Both are targets of fierce competition. Viagra™ is well known to the public while Copaxone™ is known only to MS sufferers. Was Viagra able to generate a halo effect because sexual dysfunctions are sexier than sclerosis? Is it because sexual dysfunction is perceived as a more severe problem which affects a greater number of people? Or could it be that Viagra's success is a direct result of Pfizer's advertising dollars and brand building while Teva, the generic cost-conscious player is miserly with Copaxone's advertising budget? Or maybe this a fight between 'blue' and 'white' for customer memory space?

Designing product brands is no small task, especially when the offering has limited physical manifestations such as in the case of drugs: drug competition is a question of efficacy much before it becomes a question of design. Naturally, importance is placed on package insert that documents drug competencies attention is given to the design of the package. And so we asked the question of *how can design augment and reinforce branding a product that's known more for its intellectual assets than physical ones?*

This study was aimed at establishing relationship between brand attributes that promote desired drug personalities and *color*; this, of course, assumes that color, a silent agent of meaning, is a key design lever that can positively support branding drugs such as Viagra™ and Copaxone™.

2. Why 'brand' drugs?

The impetus to brand drugs is a relatively recent phenomenon largely triggered by increasing difficulty associated with bringing drugs to market. While traditionally pharmaceuticals focused on products rather than brands, the dynamic changes in this industry caused a shift in the orientation towards branding drugs. From shortened patent life, to limited exclusivity window, intensified competitive pressures and M&A activity and FDA control, and the dramatic increase in R&D costs, the race for the next blockbuster drug among players is becoming ever more competitive and the necessity to differentiate drugs through branding is on the rise (Moss, 2001)

Drug branding presents a revolutionary challenge to an industry that championed marketing the technical quality, safety, efficacy and tolerability of the products. At the same time it also presents an opportunity for pharmaceuticals to connect with patients in a stronger and less imitable way. A study by Kapferer (1997) found that while products were known for their efficacy, branded drugs were able to generate trust and add value that way. In addition to the product features, product branding attempts to conjure up favorable images and associations and elicits emotions that would in turn build a bond between the branded drug and the patient. While branding in general can happen at the level of the company, the therapeutic area and the drug itself (Moss, 2001), the idea of branding the drug and developing its personality and emotional associations began to gain acceptance.

IMS Health's Statistics¹ noted that the top 20 branded drugs in 2000 represented over 15% of the total revenue for pharmaceutical companies. This speaks directly to the success of branding in this industry (See Appendix 1). It is important, then, that we better understand how global branding works for pharmaceutical products, and more specifically, how desired drug personality is shaped and how this personality elicits emotional bonds with patients.

¹ Source: http://www.imshealth.com/web/home/0,3153,64576068_63872702,00.html

3. How does branding work?

To address this first question we turn to Brand theory for insights. Branding has evolved over the past decades and is now viewed as entrenched in the consumer experience so that the brand selling proposition (Lindstrom, 2003) seems stronger than the actual features of the product. Consumers are attracted to the Disney brand because it promises enjoyment. Disney movie watchers are less fixated with the stories that Disney tells in its movies, and more attracted to the Disney's 'fun promise'. Nike is more about empowerment and "Just do it" (the Nike Slogan) than it is about a particular sports shoe. Coke is youth and not just a beverage. Pokemon is a complete experience conveyed through unique language and images and not a simple pack of cards that parents dread. Branding a product augments the product's features by adding the emotional value that attract and interest customers. The emotion in turn translates into a bond, a sense of loyalty that consumers hold towards the brand.

Social psychologists explain this chain effect through what is known as the C-A-B paradigm (Cognition – Emotion – Behavior). Essentially, cognition (C) determines affect (A) which in turn results in behavior (B). The distinction between cognition and affect was advocated by Zajonc (1980) who considered feelings and cognitions as two separate evaluation systems. Abelson et al's (1982) empirical investigation supported Zajonc's claim for the independence of these two systems. Thus, brands communicate an image that registers first mentally – cognitively and then translates into emotions that impact consumer behavior.

Holbrook & Batra (1987) provide an excellent review of the C-A-B paradigm research and draw attention to the usefulness of emotions as mediators between cognitions and behaviors. Their research focuses specifically on the role of pleasure arousal and content as mediators between brand messages and consumers' perceptions of and attitude towards the brand. Additional support to this school of thought is found in Edell and Burke (1987) and Woods (2004). These researchers suggest that branding involves triggering and consequently engaging consumers' emotions through brand messages to

ultimately gain a 'share of heart' (Day, 1989). Accordingly, a brand like Nike sends an empowering message– 'Just do it'. Consumers hear, then feel energized, and then act engaging in various sports activities using Nike's products and so the bond is formed and solidified.

Wansink (2003) further advances our understanding of how such bond, or brand equity, evolves. This researcher discusses a means-end theory that argues for a hierarchical order of consumer product knowledge and perception, which ranges from product attributes to consumption patterns and further to personal values. To demonstrate this Wansink uses the example of a convertible sports car. This car leads to feelings of excitement and youth that in turn support one or more of the consumer's values. While product attributes describe the technical properties of that product, consequences and values, are often related to deep emotional needs that represent the real reason why a certain brand is attractive to consumers (See Appendix 2).

Brand loyalty grows out of the brand's ability to cater to individual emotions and values. Research clearly demonstrates kids' preferences for emotions to be included in their commercial, entertainment, brands. For example, 76% of subjects said they wanted something to believe in (Lindstrom, 2003). Young consumers looked for foci to which they could attach their loyalties. Pharmaceuticals realized that developing 'drug personalities' would also improve drug brand loyalty, as drugs, like other products, have to be emotionally appealing to generate deep bonds. Still willing and interested companies faced two challenges: what attributes determine a drug personality and, how these attributes are communicated to create the desired emotional response from consumers.

4. Building and communicating drug brands

Brand personality builds on the emotional appeal of brands and is an important differentiating factor in positioning that brand. Brands, in general, can be positioned as masculine or feminine, young or old, authoritative or light hearted, radical or

conservative. They can reflect human personality traits and can align themselves closely with the aspirations of their target audience². Drugs branders often defer to personality traits such as innovative, fast-acting, relieving, and trusted.

How does a company communicate these attributes to consumers in hopes of eliciting the desired emotional response? Following the C-A-B paradigm argument one would naturally begin with conveying messages that can be registered as accepted cognitions and generate expected emotions. Typically companies would convey such messages through advertisement. Interestingly though while advertising spending has increased 8% annually, the average consumer is exposed to 9% more commercial communications each year (Shenk, 1998) and the effectiveness of such messages is on a continuous decline. For example in 1965 the average consumer remembered about 34% of the ads shown on TV while in 1990 she remembered only 8%³. Lindstrom (2003) concludes that advertising hit a wall. Clearly the C-A-B paradigm is less effective if messages are not heard or remembered and thereby have little impact on cognition.

How else then can consumer emotions be affected if not through advertisement? Design literature suggests an alternative, direct means of impacting consumer emotions. Contemporary thinking in the field of design views *designing* as a *possibility-creating activity* focused on the *relationship* between the user and the design (be it designed products, objects or environments) and the subsequent desired *experience* that is created (Hekkert, 2001). According to this view, design shifts from creating products to creating *contexts for experience* where the user is seduced to experience the designed with all their senses (Overbeeke, Djajadiningrat, Wensveen, & Hummels, 1999). By designing *contexts for experience* instead of products, objects and/or environments the focus shifts from the result *of* interaction towards the involvement *in and during* interaction (Hummels, 1999). This person-design interactive experience is *affective* in nature and involves a great variety of emotions.

² Source : <http://www.samedanltd.com/members/archives/PMPS/Spring2002/TomBlackett.htm>

³ Source : <http://www.nabs.co.nz/index.php>

Can designing the physical aspects of a drug serve as a visual manifestation of the brand that would not only reflect the brand's personality and positioning, but also create a context of experience for engaging patients' emotionally and generating the desired bond? And if so, what design levers would most successfully inspire this bonding?

5. Coloring your brand

In 1942 Lucky Strike, the cigarette brand, struck a problem. The Second World War was raging and chromium, an element essential to the green ink on their labels was in short supply. So at around the same time the American troops invaded North Africa, Lucky Strike released its new pack with its red target along with the slogan "Lucky Strike has gone to war!" Six weeks later Lucky Strike sales were up 38 percent (Lindstrom, 2003, p.44-45).

Lindstrom continues to describe the war over 'color ownership' of companies like Heinz, Coca-Cola, IBM, Orange, Hertz and others. Color is essential to the branding process because it serves as the first point of communication creating associations. Recent research on color as an emotional language (Lechner & Harrington, 2003) reveals that color carries a consistent set of meanings similar to any other linguistic instrument. In an empirical investigation of a U.S. based sample, subjects identified color associations for what a particular color is and what it is not. Furthermore, subjects clearly associated emotions to colors in consistent ways leading researchers to conclude that *color is a language of emotions*⁴.

We *postulated* that color as a design lever capable of eliciting consumer emotions, can be leveraged by pharmaceutical companies to create a desired experience to support drug personality and overall bonding with the patient. We further assumed that color as an 'emotional language' presents the opportunity to impact consumer behavior (B) directly by generating affect (A) without depending on cognition generation(C).

⁴ As discussed in the color-language research article Merriam-Webster Online Dictionary defines **language** as a systematic means of communicating ideas or feelings by the use of conventionalized signs, sounds, gestures, or marks having understood meanings, or the suggestion by objects, actions, or conditions of associated ideas or feelings. Along the same lines Crystal (1997) offers that common purposes of language include emotional expression, social interaction, recording of facts, shaping reality, providing an instrument of thought and expression of identity. We recruited these definitions to construct the argument of color as a language.

Figure 1: Intersecting Color-Emotion-Brand to create brand bond

6. Research Overview and Results

6. a. Proposition:

This inquiry was motivated by the proposition that color can be employed as a design lever to evoke emotions associated with desired drug personality in support of the drug brand.

6. b. Background:

The tablet medicine market is structured in two tiers. The majority of tablets are produced in white non-coated application. The smaller tier covers about 20 percent of tablet medicines. These appear in colors selected to support brand personality attributes. For example, drugs claiming to be innovative -cutting edge are likely to be produced in different colors than ones positioned as reliable or calming. Yet the science behind color selection decisions is still limited. In fact color decision makers often select colors they like and that intuitively appear connected with brand attributes. For example, the decision to make Viagra blue is attributed to Pfizer CEO McKinnell's known preference for that color!

6. c. Study design:

Addressing the question of branding drugs through the use of color, several methodology choices had to be made. First, we had to define what constituted relevant brand attributions. This proved difficult given the absence of brand theory relevant to attribute selection decisions. We identified twenty-two relevant drug personality and emotional attributes using an expert panel, and then defined the colors worth studying.

There was limited theory to guide the color selection and so we relied both on the limited existing literature of color studies in this area and the expert opinions of color designers in the pharmaceutical industry. Previous research on color preference reviewed a small number of primary colors: red, blue, green and yellow (see Fernberger, 1914; Garth & Porter, 1931; Jacobs & Suess, 1975; Jastrow, 1937; Kwallek, Lewis, & Robbins, 1988; Dorcus, 1926; Staples & Walton, 1933), and some have also offered conclusions regarding the importance of color value (i.e. lightness or darkness of the hue). Still focusing only on primary colors would have substantially limited the generalizability of our findings as drug personalities vary and require a greater variety of colors to select from. Therefore, we included primary, secondary and tertiary colors in the palette with values ranging from light to medium to dark.

Lastly we had to assume the potential of cultural differences in brand attributes – color associations and ensure fair representation of various geographies as proxy for cultures. This aspect of the study was particularly important to understand as a drug like Viagra much like other top blockbuster brands is positioned to serve global markets. Global brands need to carry consistent characteristics, be distributed world-wide and be promoted exactly the same way (Domzal & Unger, 1987) and so we wanted to learn if color attribution relationships remain consistent across various jurisdictions. Table 1 below presents the methodology choices made:

<p>Colors Selected</p>	<p>Red Orange Yellow / Orange Yellow Green Blue / Green Blue Purple Black</p>
<p>Attributes Selected</p>	<p>Innovative; New; Plain; First in Class; Common; Dependable; Powerful; Natural; Energizing; Safe; Fast Acting; Calming; Relieving; Trusted; Exciting; Expensive; Unhealthy; Confidence; Discomfort; Caution; Failure; Quality; Happy; Love; Interest; Disgust; Fear</p>
<p>Geographies Selected</p>	<p>US - Canada; United Kingdom; France; Germany; Spain; Italy; China; India; Japan; Korea; Brazil</p>
<p>Sample Characteristics</p>	<p>n = 2021 [with average of 160 subjects per country]; Females - 1033 (50.588%); Males - 988 (49.412%)</p>

Table 1: Methodological Choices for Studying Brand-Design Relationship

6. d. Data collection:

Data was collected using an on-line survey developed and validated by the researchers. To ensure consistency and integrity in data collection, the survey was administered by a global data collection agency.

6. f. Findings:

Our findings confirm the proposition that specific color choices are strongly associated with specific drug personality attributes, supporting the meaning attached to the drug brand. Still color meaning and color-attribute associations are rarely universal. In fact, we found that the most relevant level of analysis is the jurisdiction. Countries varied from one another in color-attribute associations and while some commonalities exist across countries, each country has a strong color-attribute vocabulary that has to be considered. Furthermore, when consistency across countries does occur, reds black and white are used for the most part. For example an attribute like ‘powerful’ is associated with strong medium red (7/11 countries); ‘love’ with dark red (7/11 countries) ‘energizing’ with dark

red (6/11 countries), 'fast acting' with medium red (6/11 countries), 'plain' with white (8/11 countries), 'common' with white (8/11 countries) 'dependable' with white (8/11 countries), 'discomfort' with black (6/11 countries), 'fear' with black (6/11 countries), 'unhealthy' with black (9/11 countries); 'disgust' with black (6/11 countries) and 'failure' with black (6/11 countries).

Since our attribution list included both emotions and drug personality attributes, we also conducted an analysis looking at the triangulation of emotional attributes, drug personality attributes and color. This analysis yielded particularly strong results for love, fear and disgust, in dark red, medium red and black. Other findings of interest included:

- Light purple is not associated with positive attributes. When purple is used it is dark in value and is associated with newness attributes like innovation.
- Gray is the most 'not associated with positive attributes' color of all
- Black is typically associated with attributes like discomfort, unhealthy and failure across most of the countries studied
- Dark and medium red as well as white are used to describe many attributes, both positive and negative across most countries making these colors 'all-inclusive' and thus the least 'ownable'. These are the strongest color choices for communicating a message that is not designed to be very specific
- Tertiary colors – blue-green and yellow-orange are least recognized and when used they are associated with more sophisticated terms such as innovation and first in class.

7. Conclusions and Future Directions:

Our study showed clear associations between color and brand attributes such as emotion and drug personality. Such associations are consistent and suggest that color as a 'meaning agent' tends to trigger emotional response. Within the C-A-B paradigm, color influences affect (A) in a consistent manner. The branding of what might be viewed as intellectual assets [drugs] can therefore be accomplished by using design [color lever] consciously and knowledgably to communicate and reinforce desired brand personality

characteristics through the physical facet of a drug. This statement is not without limitations, however.

Geography played a central role in influencing the color-attribute association. Despite some universality in associations, much of the emphasis was placed on contextualizing color-attribute associations within geography. This finding is particularly meaningful to brands that position themselves as global. While consistency is central to global brands, contextual color-attribute associations suggest that color selection decisions might need to be geography-sensitive.

Drugs are launched in multiple countries and are differentiated through the use of multiple brand personality attributes in competitive environments. Often in these markets color is either owned by existing competitors or constrained by regulators; all of this makes color ownership increasingly challenging to manage. While our data showed significant associations of color-attribute within and across geographies, it was difficult to construct a 'color profile' for a drug that has multiple brand personality attributes and is intended for multiple geographies. In the analyses, we attempted to sidestep this by grouping countries as well as attributes. The analyses revealed that groups of countries (not necessarily by region) have preferred color palettes and groups of attributes are also linked to a preferred color palette (See Appendix C). Further research is needed to explore the impact of attribute and geographic diversity on color decisions to increase the usability of these results. Specifically, additional exploration is required to better understand not only how color-attribute associations vary across geographies but also why such differences exist and what should they be attributed to (i.e., cultural traditions, or any other geography related factors).

This study supports the proposition that branding can use color as the design lever to support brand personality, influence affect and generate desired brand perceptions and bond. The role of color goes far beyond being a simple visual element that serves as a point-of-memory to remind people of the iconic facet of the brand like in the case of Shell, DHL, Jet Blue or Orange. Viagra's Blue may very well be remembered also

because of the confidence, dependable, quality, innovative, first in class and happy attributes associated with blue (See Appendix D). Color leverage seems a promising contributor to branding efforts.

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Appendix A - Performance of top 20 brands in the pharmaceutical industry, 2000

#	Product Brand	Pharma Company	\$B	Therapeutic area
1	Losec	AstraZeneca	5.43	Metabolic
2	Lipitor	Pfizer	4.33	Cardiovascular
3	Zocor	Merck	3.63	Cardiovascular
4	Norvasc	Pfizer	3.06	Cardiovascular
5	Prozac	Lilly	2.66	Central nervous system
6	Ogastro	Abbott	2.57	Metabolic
7	Seroxat	Smithkline Beechman	2.22	Central nervous system
8	Zyperxa	Lilly	2.19	Central nervous system
9	Zoloft	Pfizer	2.01	Central nervous system
10	Erypo	J&J	1.99	Blood forming organs
11	Claritine	Schering-Plough	1.95	Respiratory system
12	Epogen	Amgen	1.95	Blood forming organs
13	Celebrex	Pharmacia	1.90	Central nervous system
14	Augmentin	Smithkline Beechman	1.84	Anti-infectives
15	Risperdal	J&J	1.60	Central nervous system
16	Ciproxin	Bayer	1.58	Anti-infectives
17	Galucophage	BMS	1.54	Metabolic
18	Renitec	Merck	1.50	Cardiovascular
19	Pravachol	BMS	1.47	Cardiovascular
20	Zithromax	Pfizer	1.40	Anti-infectives
	Sub Total	Branded Drugs	46.81	
	Total	Industry	298	

Source: IMS Health

Appendix B - Illustration of a hierarchical value map

Appendix C - Examples of attribute groupings and color associations

	Love	Happy	Interest	Fear	Disgust
Brazil					
China					
France					
Germany					
India					
Italy					
Japan					
Korea					
Spain					
UK					
US					

Emotional attributes

	Trust	Safe	Natural	Cautious	Unhealthy
Brazil					
China					
France					
Germany					
India					
Italy					
Japan					
Korea					
Spain					
UK					
US					

Drug personality attributes (Safety category)

Appendix D - Blue - Attribute associations

Blue	Light								
Brazil				Confidence Common	Trust Calming	First in Class Quality	Happy	Exciting	Safe
China	Disgust								
France	Innovation	Disgust	Failure	Calming			Relieving	First in Class	
Germany							Happy		
Japan									
Korea							Quality		
India	Calming								
Italy							Natural		
Spain	Cautious			Innovation					
UK	Innovation	Safe	Energizing						
US							Confidence	Dependable	Quality